

Scientific article

A control-oriented load surrogate model based on sector-averaged inflow quantities: capturing damage for unawaked, waked, wake-steering and curtailed wind turbines

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Published on: Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Volume 2767, Dynamics, control, and monitoring

Abstract: *This paper presents a novel approach to constructing a load surrogate model. It aims to estimate any wind turbine's damage equivalent loads (DELs) regardless of its position and under various farm control actions. The model relies solely on local inflow quantities (sector averaged wind speeds and turbulence intensities) and local control parameters (rotor speed, pitch angle, and yaw misalignment). Despite its highly simplified representation of the complex behavior of the turbulent wind field, wake effects, and controller dynamics, these quantities prove sufficient to characterize DELs. The paper demonstrates the training of this load model within a simulation environment. Validation results using a different wind farm configuration indicate that the surrogate can accurately predict fatigue loads for both unawaked and waked turbines, encompassing scenarios of wake steering and induction control.*

Link to article: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/2767/3/032019>

SUDOCO is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101122256). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.